

A 4P framework for dimension of the societal impact of the REF 2021

Xiao Yang¹, Yan Zeng², and Junpeng Yuan³

¹yangxiao@mail.las.ac.cn

Chinese Academy of Sciences, National Science Library, No. 33 Beisihuan Xilu, Beijing 100190 (China)
University of Chinese Academy of Sciences, School of Economics and Management, University of Chinese Academy of Sciences, Department of Information Resources Management, No. 3, South Yitiao, Zhongguancun, Beijing 100190 (China)

²zengy@mail.las.ac.cn

Chinese Academy of Sciences, National Science Library, No. 33 Beisihuan Xilu, Beijing 100190 (China)

³yuanjp@mail.las.ac.cn

Chinese Academy of Sciences, National Science Library, No. 33 Beisihuan Xilu, Beijing 100190 (China)
Academy of Sciences, Department of Information Resources Management, No. 3, South Yitiao, Zhongguancun, Beijing 100190 (China)

Introduction

Since the 21st century, developed nations and regions have incrementally changed how science and technology are evaluated. It's becoming more common to assess research not only in terms of its academic impact on the scientific community, but also its social impact on economic and social development (LIU & ZHONG, 2020). The global reform of science and technology evaluation is moving towards the forefront of social impact of research, which is increasingly important in higher education and research policy (Fotaki, 2021). This is also a major challenge currently facing the academic community. Therefore, this paper focuses on the content analysis of 2469 research impact cases about societal impact in REF2021 to present the characteristics of social impact of scientific research achievements in British universities, so as to provide references for multi-value evaluation and promote the reform process of scientific research evaluation in the world.

Data and Method

Since 2014, REF has adopted the "case+template" approach to evaluate the impact, change or benefit of scientific research on the economy, society, culture, environment, or quality of life and so on (Pan & Pee, 2020). There are 6361 cases in the REF2021 case dataset, divided into eight categories: "societal"; "technological"; "cultural"; "health"; "environmental"; "economics"; "legal" and "political", and we chose 2469 cases with a 'societal' label. Each case in REF 2021 consist of several elements, such as 'Title', 'Summary of the impact', 'Underpinning research', 'Details of the impact' and so on. This paper aims to answer the following three questions through a textual analysis of the 'title' and 'Summary of the impact': (1) How is "social impact" demonstrated? (2) How are the Disciplines of "social impact" distributed? (3) How does "social impact" happen?

Figure 1. A roadmap for text analysis.

To analyze the dimensions of social impact assessment, we extract terms from the text content of 2469 cases to obtain a glossary of high-frequency terms by using CorTexT Manager (Breucker, Cointet, Abdo, et al., 2016) in the first step; The next step is that based on glossary, we conduct case analysis and text mining of the case and the guidelines of REF and eliminate irrelevant words, so that it could present the word list of high-frequency related terms describing "social impact" and summarize the assessment dimension of social impact. The word list includes 25 feature words (Tab 1) and 5 words representing "change" (enhance; change; influence; transform; improve). We also make a co-occurrence network of 30 keywords (Fig 2). By analyzing and clustering keywords, we propose a new 4P framework.

Research Conclusions

How is "social impact" demonstrated?

A new 4P framework of perception, participation, practice and policy was proposed: (1) Perceptual impact: The research raises public awareness and understanding, improves scientific quality, and forms diversified social values. (2) Public participation: The research increases opportunities for public participation and collaboration, enhances interest and enthusiasm for participating in science, and promotes the collaboration among stakeholders. (3) Practical efficiency: The research provides new methods, tools, and improved organization, increasing opportunities and access to information and services for the public. Additionally, research results can be translated to benefit social welfare for the public. (4) Instrumental impact: The research influences policy, standards and legislation to

facilitate the inclusiveness, applicability, propagation and availability of revised policies. By further observing the relationship between the four dimensions, we can find that policy guides practice, practice promotes public participation, and public participation also causes a change in public consciousness (fig.2). Scientific research has a multi-dimensional overlapping comprehensive impact, rather than a single dimension.

Note: The co-occurrence frequency ≥ 1

Figure 2. A co-occurrence map of terms related to social impact.

How are the disciplines of "social impact" distributed?

The REF case database includes 34 disciplines, categorized into four panels: Biomedicine (A), Natural science (B), Social science (C) and humanities (D). Among the 'societal impact cases', Unit A has 316 cases, Unit B has 169 cases, Unit C has 1356 cases, and Unit D has 628 cases.

As shown in Tab1, practical efficiency and instrumental impact have a higher proportion than perceptual impact and public participation in general. In terms of disciplines, the proportion of practical efficiency in Unit A is higher than that in the other three dimensions. In unit B, the highest proportion is public participation, and the co-occurrence frequency of the word "understand" in perceptual impact is relatively high. The proportion of instrumental impact is the highest, followed by practical efficiency in unit C. The proportions of the four dimensions in Unit D are balanced, but the perceptual impact is slightly lower than that of the other three dimensions. In general, there are clear differences between various disciplines; and perceptual impact needs more attention in the future.

Table 1. Distribution of Social Impact Terms by Discipline.

Discipline	Term	Panel A (Biomedicine)				Panel B (Natural science)				Panel C (Social science)				Panel D (Humanities)			
		Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage				
Public participation	Public participation	15	4.7%	25	14.8%	10	0.7%	15	1.1%	10	0.7%	15	2.4%				
	Public participation	15	4.7%	25	14.8%	10	0.7%	15	1.1%	10	0.7%	15	2.4%				
	Public participation	15	4.7%	25	14.8%	10	0.7%	15	1.1%	10	0.7%	15	2.4%				
	Public participation	15	4.7%	25	14.8%	10	0.7%	15	1.1%	10	0.7%	15	2.4%				
Practical Efficiency	Practical Efficiency	25	7.8%	35	20.1%	45	3.3%	55	4.0%	65	4.8%	75	12.1%				
	Practical Efficiency	25	7.8%	35	20.1%	45	3.3%	55	4.0%	65	4.8%	75	12.1%				
	Practical Efficiency	25	7.8%	35	20.1%	45	3.3%	55	4.0%	65	4.8%	75	12.1%				
	Practical Efficiency	25	7.8%	35	20.1%	45	3.3%	55	4.0%	65	4.8%	75	12.1%				
Instrumental Impact	Instrumental Impact	35	10.8%	45	26.0%	55	4.0%	65	4.8%	75	12.1%	85	13.7%				
	Instrumental Impact	35	10.8%	45	26.0%	55	4.0%	65	4.8%	75	12.1%	85	13.7%				
	Instrumental Impact	35	10.8%	45	26.0%	55	4.0%	65	4.8%	75	12.1%	85	13.7%				
	Instrumental Impact	35	10.8%	45	26.0%	55	4.0%	65	4.8%	75	12.1%	85	13.7%				
Perceptual impact	Perceptual impact	45	13.9%	55	31.3%	65	4.8%	75	5.5%	85	13.7%	95	15.1%				
	Perceptual impact	45	13.9%	55	31.3%	65	4.8%	75	5.5%	85	13.7%	95	15.1%				
	Perceptual impact	45	13.9%	55	31.3%	65	4.8%	75	5.5%	85	13.7%	95	15.1%				
	Perceptual impact	45	13.9%	55	31.3%	65	4.8%	75	5.5%	85	13.7%	95	15.1%				

How does "social impact" happen?

Through the analysis of the REF cases, it is found that there are mainly four ways to generate social impact, and the corresponding relationship between the four paths and the four dimensions of social

impact is shown in Tab 2. (1) Science popularization activities, such as exhibitions, media publicity, laboratory openings, theme day activities and science popularization in the community. (2) Scientific and technological service activities, such as scientific exchange and discussion, innovation and development. (3) Social service activities, such as technical guidance, education and training. (4) Government service activities, such as policy reform and decision-making consultation.

Table 2. Mechanisms of Social Impact.

Category	Perceptual impact	Public participation	Practical efficiency	Instrumental impact
Science popularization activities	✓	✓		
Science and technology service activities		✓	✓	
Social service activities	✓	✓	✓	
Government service activities				✓

Conclusion

This paper analyzed 2469 assessment cases of social impact of REF, summarized the 4P framework of social impact and its occurrence ways, and discussed the disciplinary differences of social impact. The Research is in Progress and the next work plan is (1) Identify the impact dimensions and happen ways of social impact in STEM fields, namely, panels A and B, further condense the path of social impact generated by natural science; (2) Construct a multi-level evaluation system for social impact evaluation, including evaluation dimensions, happen channels, stakeholders, etc.

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